
Removal of Pharmaceuticals from Wastewater by means of adsorption on activated carbon, polymeric resins and molecularly imprinted polymers

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1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment even at very low concentrations can lead to uncertain toxic effects on both human beings and aquatic ecosystems, hence the importance of a global worldwide collaboration to obtain the monitoring data that will help to make decision to reduce the environmental impacts of pharmaceuticals (Wilkinson et al., 2022). The concern about these micropollutants and their potential toxicity is increasing, as proved by the draft of the new EU wastewater directive, which requires an average 80% removal of at least 6 pharmaceuticals. Carbamazepine and diclofenac, widely detected in water bodies, were chosen as target compounds in this work. Carbamazepine (CBZ) is an anticonvulsant and analgesic drug used to control seizures and to treat pain resulting from trigeminal neuralgia. Ibuprofen (IBU) belongs to the category of Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), and it is one of the most used analgesic, antipyretic and anti-inflammatory drugs. Both are poorly removed by conventional wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). The main treatments that can be employed to remove pharmaceuticals are physical (adsorption, membranes) and chemical (advanced oxidation processes like ozonation, UV/H₂O₂, O₃/H₂O₂) (Loganathan et al., 2023). This work investigates pharmaceutical removal by adsorption, in consideration of its low capital investment, applicability at low concentrations and absence of production of toxic byproducts. Molecularly Imprinted Polymers (MIPs) were developed and tested to find non-conventional materials as valid alternatives to commercial adsorbent like activated carbon (Gutiérrez et al., 2023). MIPs, produced by radical polymerization, are characterized by highly selective sites with specific affinity for the target molecule for which they are developed, high mechanical and chemical resistance and the possibility of being regenerated multiple times (Parlapiano et al., 2021). The latter is a very significant aspect to consider for application in a packed bed column, as desorption from activated carbon is expensive and usually performed off-site.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Adsorbent materials

The tested commercial adsorbent materials are Amberlite XAD16N, a non-ionic styrene-divinylbenzene adsorption solid phase, and activated carbon Norit GAC 1240 W.

MIPs were synthesized by bulk polymerization according to the following procedure proposed by Cantarella et al. (2019): 0.2 mmol of template (target pharmaceutical), 2 mmol of monomer and 8 mL of porogen (acetonitrile), were mixed in a three-necked flask for 15-20 min (pre-polymerization step) then, 10 mmol of cross-linker and 5.1 mmol of initiator (AIBN) were added and the mixture was degassed with a nitrogen flow for 5 min and then sealed and placed in a silicon oil bath at 70° C for 4 h. Several MIPs were produced for each target pharmaceutical by combining different monomers and cross-linkers. Each MIP was labelled with the acronym MIP_J_X_Y_Z, where: J indicates the target pharmaceutical (CBZ or IBU), X indicates the monomer (methacrylic acid (MAA), 2-vinylpyridine (2VP), 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), methacrylamide (MAAM), itaconic acid (ITA), eugenol (EUG)), Y indicates the cross-linker (a difunctional one that is ethylene glycol methacrylate (EG), and a trifunctional one that

is trimethylolpropane triacrylate (TRIM)), and Z indicates the template removal procedure (L1: washing the polymer with a Buchner by a continuous flow of 200 mL of methanol and acetic acid 9:1 v/v; L2: putting the polymer under agitation in 50 mL of methanol and acetic acid 9:1 v/v for 30 min at 30°C and refreshing the solvent for 3 times).

2.2 Analytical methods

CBZ and IBU concentrations were determined by a Waters UPLC-MS. The UPLC-MS method employs an Acquity UPLC BEH C18 column, a mobile phase composed of 60:40 water:acetonitrile (v/v) and 0.1% of formic acid and a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min.

2.3 Adsorption isotherms and continuous flow tests

The batch isotherm tests were performed in real WWTP effluent, spiked with CBZ or IBU to reach the desired concentrations. The concentration of the adsorbent was 1 g_{adsorbent}/L, the temperature of the rotary shaker was set at 22 °C and the rotational speed was 160 rpm. For CBZ, a continuous flow test of adsorption on Norit was conducted under the following conditions: empty bed contact time (EBCT) 23 min; bed height 40 cm; superficial velocity 1 m/h; particle size 0.7 – 1.4 mm. The test was fed with an actual WWTP effluent.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Adsorption isotherms of carbamazepine and ibuprofen adsorption

The adsorption isotherms obtained for IBU indicate that Norit outperformed all the other materials, followed by the neutral polymeric resin XAD16N. Among the MIPs, the best resulted the one with eugenol as monomer and TRIM as cross-linker. In particular, Norit allowed the attainment of sorbed phase IBU concentrations of a few mg/g even at the low IBU concentrations typical of municipal wastewaters, despite the presence of a relevant COD in the WWTP effluent used for the tests (40-45 mg COD/L). The isotherms of both Norit and XAD16N resulted linear in the tested concentration range, with linear adsorption constants of 8.9 L/g for Norit and 2.3 L/g for XAD16N.

In the adsorption isotherms obtained for CBZ the performances of Norit resulted equal to those of XAD16N. Interestingly, the MIP produced with methacrylic acid as monomer and TRIM as cross-linker resulted in high performances, close to those of both Norit and XAD16N. Further isotherm and continuous flow tests are in progress with this MIP. The isotherms of Norit, XAD16N and MIP_CBZ_MAA_TRIM_L2 resulted linear in the tested concentration range, with linear adsorption constants significantly higher than those obtained for IBU: 73 L/g for Norit, 65 L/g for MIP_CBZ_MAA_TRIM_L2 and 44 L/g for XAD16N. With regard to MIP_CBZ_MAA_TRIM, the results indicate that the second template removal procedure (L2), characterized by a batch process and a triple refreshing of the solvent, resulted in significantly better performances than the first removal procedure (L1).

3.2 Continuous flow test of carbamazepine adsorption

The preliminary results of the continuous flow test of CBZ adsorption on activated carbon Norit at a 23 min EBCT indicate that, after the treatment of 6000 bed volumes of WWTP effluent, the breakthrough curve resulted just at the beginning, with an effluent CBZ concentration equal to 0.3% of the influent concentration. Even though these results are preliminary and the test is still in progress, the observed performance appears to be higher than that typically reported in the literature for CBZ adsorption on activated carbon. For example, at 23 min EBCT, Benstoem et al., (2017) report the attainment of a 20% breakpoint at 10000-15000 bed volumes.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work showed the effectiveness of both Norit GAC 1240 W and XAD16N in removing both carbamazepine and ibuprofen from real WWTP effluent, in both batch and continuous flow tests. In addition, a MIP containing methacrylic acid as monomer and trimethylolpropane triacrylate as cross-linker resulted in CBZ adsorption performances close to those of both Norit and XAD16N. Given the high selectivity of MIPs, this material could present relevant advantages over activated carbon, such as the possibility to regenerate it in-situ at the WWTP and to re-use over a very high number of adsorption / desorption cycles. Continuous flow tests of adsorption and desorption on MIPs are in progress in order to verify this hypothesis.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CBZ, carbamazepine
EBCT, empty bed contact time
IBU, ibuprofen
MIP, molecularly imprinted polymer
NSAID, Non-Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drug
WWTP, wastewater treatment plant